

Winning the New Cold War & World War 3.0

Dealing with inoculating the West - especially Americans - against Marxism, Stalinism, Maoism, fascism, Nationalism/Socialism (Nazis), and the modern threats of jihadism, anarchism, Critical Theories, progressivism/antifa (brown shirts), and the greedy excesses of croney & vulture capitalism and materialism.

A short, concise, no holds barred, kind-spirited, martially mean, anti-pacifist, pro-peace document to quickly open the eyes, awaken the mind, quicken the spirit, and beget courage among the (mostly) innocent populace of lazy, despondent, concerned, slow-to-react moderate middle and independents (or those left behind by the left and refusers of neo-cons and alt-right)

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August 2021

Part 4 in a Series, Part 6 of the Recommended Pack¹, and as a bonus, a never-before-released memo² given to Congressman Andy Barr's office in January of 2019 **before** the start of WW3.0

ABSTRACT

My friends, we are losing a war you weren't told existed. If the audience is not yet aware of the takeover and the exact nature of the players involved, then this document will 1) get the audience up to speed with homework of what to read/study, 2) prepare a formulaic list of things to do for the individual and 3) for the western society (churches, institutions, etc.), which 4) while unable to stop the flow of money towards evil at the moment will in the future provide for a new foundation of the west on all levels from spiritual to material dimensions, and everything in between. Finally, martial recommendations will be made, along with access to an example template document, for replication in your local to regional jurisdictions while it is still legal to think independently and act against the wishes of the BORG/consensus leftist ideologies who want freedom to persecute those who want freedom just to be left alone. This was the main reason for the American Revolution and what constitutes Americanism (to be a patriot in America or around the world is to often be staunchly against nationalism) abroad.

KEYWORDS: Liberty - Freedom - Digital War - Asymmetric Attack - COVID - civil war - humanistic

¹ "Calculating Innate Shi," "Asymmetric Vulnerabilities of the US," "China vs. the World," "21st Century Cyberattacks," "Airsoft Team," & "Concerning Sustainable Protection of Family & Business" - see References for full titles and links

² <https://bit.ly/3COs8Om>

Introduction	3
What is The New Cold War?	3
What is World War 3.0?	5
Who are the Antagonists?	6
What are the Allies doing or Not doing to Prepare?	7
Table 1 - Allies of the US and NATO	7
Catching Up to Speed	11
The New World Order Plans	11
The Deep State	12
The Muslim Brotherhood	13
Side Players	15
Modern Industrialized Slavery	16
Neocolonialism	17
Future Empires	17
Solution Sets	18
Table 2 - Solution sets; Red is Attack, Green is Support, Blue is Neutralize	18
Value Systems Wars (Culture Wars)	18
Preparing Your Family & Friends (Inoculation)	19
Action Steps Checklist	20
Author Further Recommends	21
Conclusion	22
References	23

Introduction

As promised, brief and concise summary and basic citations. Maybe not brief enough for some. But after all, it's a lot of information in a compressed space.

What is The New Cold War?

After the Cold War ended in 1991, the world breathed a sigh of relief. Unfortunately 3 seeds of the future Cold War were, already at that time, at play. The first is that Nazi scientists and academia were invited to the United States and Britain³ to share technical expertise⁴. They also taught students⁵, and ostensibly infected them.⁶ Primarily they infiltrated the CIA⁷ and the CIA made use of their ideas to subvert truth⁸ in America⁹ and abroad.¹⁰ The CIA became the primary leader of the Deep State¹¹. With the rise of brown shirts¹², technical censorship¹³, and anti-semitism¹⁴, we can be sure that National Socialist¹⁵ programmes are at play once again, and openly now.

Secondly, the communists had been making inroads in America since the 1930s¹⁶, making friends with Democrats as high up as the Roosevelt administration¹⁷. However after the 1950s era McCarthyism and the Rosenberg spy scandal¹⁸, it went underground until the 1960s where it re-emerged as Civil Rights extremism¹⁹. At this time, also, early strains of jihadism infiltrated the Civil Rights and especially the more extreme Black Power movements²⁰. The results of their arrests and exposure were a general inoculation that lasted up until

3

<https://www.usatoday.com/story/news/factcheck/2020/09/16/fact-check-nazi-scientists-brought-u-s-operation-paperclip/5690870002/>

4

<https://www.smithsonianmag.com/smart-news/why-us-government-brought-nazi-scientists-america-after-world-war-ii-180961110/>

⁵ <https://physicstoday.scitation.org/doi/10.1063/PT.6.4.20180926a/full/>

⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Operation_Paperclip

⁷ https://ips-dc.org/the_cias_worst-kept_secret_newly_declassified_files_confirm_united_states_collaboration_with_nazis/

⁸ <https://www.nytimes.com/2014/10/27/us/in-cold-war-us-spy-agencies-used-1000-nazis.html>

⁹ "We'll know our disinformation program is complete when everything the American public believes is false." William Casey, CIA Director 1981-1987

<https://kundaliniandcelltowers.com/Did%20CIA%20Director%20William%20Casey%20really%20say%20We%20will%20k%20now%20our%20disinformation%20program%20is%20complete%20when%20everything%20the%20American%20public%20believes%20is%20false-Quora.pdf> [the fact that Barbara Honnigar's testimony was removed is highly suspicious considering the topic]

¹⁰ <https://fas.org/irp/cia/product/dcia090707.html>

¹¹ The exact connections between the NWO and CIA are difficult to research. Primarily President Bush, a former CIA director, and son of Nazi sympathizer Prescott Bush

(<https://www.theguardian.com/world/2004/sep/25/usa.secondworldwar>), and his son, President George W Bush, a neocon and member of the Skull & Bones Society, is used as the evidence prima facia.

¹² Anti-fa (fascists who call themselves anti-fascist) who dress all in black, masks, and assault random people are defacto Brown Shirts.

<https://www.timesrecordnews.com/story/opinion/2018/08/20/letter-antifa-behaves-like-hitlers-brown-shirts/1037002002/> & <https://www.statesman.com/story/special/2020/08/17/opinion-looking-at-history-of-anti-facismrsquo-movement/42488539/>

¹³ <https://www.truenewshub.com/dailywire/timeline-big-techs-not-so-brief-history-of-censoring-donald-trump/>

¹⁴ <https://blogs.timesofisrael.com/the-leftist-architects-of-the-anti-israeli-bias/>

¹⁵ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Nazi-Party>

¹⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/History_of_the_Communist_Party_USA

¹⁷ <https://historynewsnetwork.org/article/171833>

¹⁸ <https://www.history.com/this-day-in-history/rosenbergs-executed>

¹⁹ <https://www.npr.org/templates/story/story.php?storyId=123771194>

²⁰ https://www.clingendael.org/sites/default/files/2016-02/20120000_meijer_whatsoever_happened_to_the_islamists.pdf

the neocon-led Iraq War fiasco post 2005. But the Communist and now-mixed Socialist elements made continuous inroads with academia from the 1970s through the 1990s^{21 22}, and again after 2008²³. The third, more blanket element was that the USA was strengthening ties with Beijing from the Nixon Administration on. However after 1989's Tiananmen Square Massacre²⁴, it should have ceased²⁵. Instead, long laid plans of the NWO and Deep State began to take effect and China became the "Tiger With Wings"²⁶ GDP powerhouse starting around 1991. So while one communist regime fell which should have knocked out all communism and socialism, instead the capitalist West and NGOs like the World Bank and IMF propped up their future rivals in the CCP and Politburo. At the time, it seemed that winning the Cold War proved the West would always win because of liberal values²⁷ and capitalism²⁸. Instead, China observed the Gulf War and adopted a new paradigm deemed "Unrestricted Warfare."²⁹ It was a limited doctrine that gained steam only because of the developments of the Internet, web 2.0, smart phones, the adoption of Operations Research branch called Analytics by big tech companies and China, and, of course social media which enables Social Credit programmes³⁰.

But the propaganda took hold because of the 2008 mortgage meltdown which "poisoned the well" in over half a dozen ways for entire generations of susceptible students; especially as it fell on the heels of the phoney Iraq War and after the notorious "don't tase me bro" incident³¹. At this time the extremists of the 1960s and 70s had many dedicated students³², now with the leveraging power of the Internet and aforementioned technologies. When the US Marines concluded "Unrestricted Warfare" could not work in practicality, it was just pre web 2.0 and social media/smartphone era, in 2005.³³ There was another reaction in 2012.³⁴ This was a major mistake of the US military complex, and because of the arrogance (or infiltration by Nazi elements and secret societies³⁵) of the neocons, it was an undetected threat even as the Federal Reserve begged China to build ghost cities³⁶. No one dealt with the CDO problem, which has also resurfaced³⁷. By the time of the Obama Administration, the weakening of NATO was well underway³⁸ and despite huge stock market gains from 2010 forward³⁹ millions of youth, educated by socialists, unaware (as Occupy Wall Street demonstrated) how either capitalism, stock markets, or civics works⁴⁰... began to cross-infect ideas between communists, socialists (and

²¹ <https://www.jstor.org/stable/41820996>

²² https://www.academia.edu/6323380/The_Battle_in_Seattle_Its_Significance_for_Education

²³ The mortgage meltdown and phoney Iraq War, as well as revelations about the 9/11 Truth, led to understandable reversal in nationalism into serious distrust in the financial system, and America in general. In addition, the new President was entirely critical of the US power structure in the world, and while anti-Israel and pro-drone of Islamic countries... was noticeably a weakener of the NATO support structure, even allowing Russia to annex the Crimea from the Ukraine. Some have then speculated the President was a puppet of the NWO, considering he was foreign born (still a citizen) and also was elected despite being a junior citizen. He received, regardless, large amounts of money from Chinese donors.

<https://thehill.com/opinion/columnists/dick-morris/261109-obamas-foreign-donors> &

<https://www.investors.com/politics/editorials/obama-campaign-raises-illegal-cash-overseas/>

²⁴ <https://www.piie.com/commentary/speeches-papers/case-89-2>

²⁵ <https://www.nbr.org/publication/the-impact-of-tiananmen-on-chinas-foreign-policy/>

²⁶ 如虎添翼 – Like adding wings to a tiger

²⁷ Libertad, fraternidad, igualdad, Lockian values, Declaration of Independence, Bill of Rights, Due Process, etc.

²⁸ <https://www.nytimes.com/2018/02/07/magazine/the-rise-of-china-and-the-fall-of-the-free-trade-myth.html>

²⁹ <https://www.c4i.org/unrestricted.pdf>

³⁰ <https://www.wired.co.uk/article/china-social-credit-system-explained>

³¹ Note: the student was tased only after asking Sen. John Kerry about his Skull & Bones membership

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=r7Qef8oPmag>

³² <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.147.6141&rep=rep1&type=pdf>

³³ <https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/pdfs/ADA509132.pdf>

³⁴ <https://www.hSDL.org/?view&did=812463>

³⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1wXf08-42x4>

³⁶ <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2015-08-06/hank-paulson-prods-china-to-rethink-urban-plans-save-the-planet>

³⁷ <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/b/bespoke-cdo.asp>

³⁸ <https://www.wsj.com/articles/SB10001424052702303802104579449571957045910>

³⁹ <https://www.cnn.com/interactive/2019/business/stock-market-by-president/index.html>

⁴⁰ <https://www.baltimoresun.com/opinion/op-ed/bs-ed-goldberg-occupy-wall-street-20111011-story.html>

even anti-government neonazis: the alt-right), identitarians, jihadists, and especially the ever-opportunistic and underemployed anarchists⁴¹. Infections of conservatism, liberalism, libertarianism, and independents began in earnest.⁴² Obvious capitalists began to tout socialism^{43 44 45} and lie about the Scandinavians⁴⁶ while ignoring outright the ongoing collapses of Zimbabwe⁴⁷, Venezuela⁴⁸, Cuba⁴⁹, and South Africa^{50 51}.

Populism and general patriotism (such as Brexit⁵²) fought back, but now the underlying technical power structure was in place. At the top of the heap leading the way into this 1984-style “Brave New World” was the Chinese Communist Party and its sympathizers in the New World Order. By 2019 the groundwork laid, the New Cold War was underway, and the world was set for an asymmetric attack called Event-201 aka COVID-19.⁵³ China was ground zero, but quickly the situation was exported *purposefully* worldwide into 2020 lockdowns (except in China where they quickly fully reopened⁵⁴ and kept pumping out viruses⁵⁵ and capitalist products to support their growing power worldwide). Small efforts to combat neocolonialism ensued, but they have been met with strange internal resistances, mostly from paid actors and Deep State protagonists. Sies are outed, but prosecution fails because the Cold War infiltration has infected DA offices throughout the west. They prosecute “homegrown terrorism” by labeling patriots racists and extremists, while allowing actual anarchy and communist revolution to go unchecked. Identity Politics infects schools and polarizes families, further weakening the west’s immune system, while Axis enemies remain staunchly homogenist, xenophobic, and highly nationalist-central power and authority regimes. This makes them extremely strong militarily, while the NATO allies weaken themselves with ID politics, Critical Theory, and generally ridiculous policies which leaders are afraid to speak out against.

What is World War 3.0?⁵⁶

How do the new Axis powers attack and weaken the (so strong, theoretically) Allies? How to weaken NATO? Aside from classic art of war methods like deception and divide and conquer, it is primarily by using the West’s openness, trust, and digital internet against itself. The Big Lie becomes many thousands of unstoppable, post-fact, postmodern lies which are continuously propagated. That which the Axis does, it projects as an evil onto the patriots, the Christians, and the Allies in general. While the West provides data, the Axis will lie about data or refuse to provide it. While the West will provide property and IP protection to stimulate innovation, China will steal and refuse to provide such protections for their citizens or worldwide companies. While justice is (rarely) found in western courts, in China you see a 99% conviction rate, and in places like North Korea or Pol Pot’s Cambodia, anyone can lie about anyone and use politics to get them

⁴¹ <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1157049.pdf>

⁴² <https://iea.org.uk/the-myth-of-libertarian-socialism/> &

<https://novaramedia.com/2016/09/16/what-is-libertarian-communism/>

⁴³ <https://thehill.com/opinion/finance/434040-capitalists-pose-the-biggest-threat-to-capitalism-not-socialists>

⁴⁴

<https://www.pewresearch.org/politics/2019/10/07/in-their-own-words-behind-americans-views-of-socialism-and-capitalism/>

⁴⁵ Here’s an article to you, capitalist liar claiming to be Socialist, Bernie Sanders:

<https://www.heritage.org/international-economies/commentary/socialism-vs-capitalism-one-clear-winner>

⁴⁶ <https://www.lifeinnorway.net/scandinavian-socialism/>

⁴⁷ <https://www.jstor.org/stable/29766844>

⁴⁸ <https://www.investors.com/politics/editorials/zimbabwes-coup-venezuelas-default-and-the-ongoing-failure-of-socialism/>

⁴⁹ <https://www.aljazeera.com/economy/2021/7/16/cuba-protests-the-economic-woes-helping-drive-discontent>

⁵⁰ <https://www.ascleiden.nl/publications/south-african-communist-party-and-collapse-soviet-union>

⁵¹

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/309320320_The_South_African_Communist_Party_in_the_context_of_the_collapse_of_socialism_in_the_Soviet_Union

⁵² <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/b/brexit.asp>

⁵³ <https://www.centerforhealthsecurity.org/event201/videos.html>

⁵⁴ <https://fortune.com/2020/04/20/coronavirus-reopening-the-economy-china-covid-19/>

⁵⁵ Aka “variants”

⁵⁶ This slideshow may help as well <https://bit.ly/37FikYx>

canceled or even executed. Cancel Culture arrived in America in 2018, with the cancelling of “conspiracy theorist” Alex Jones⁵⁷, and has rapidly advanced⁵⁸, via Web 2.0⁵⁹ “Big Tech” (FAANG⁶⁰) censorship to the President of the United States⁶¹, Senators⁶², and Federal and State Congressmen⁶³. How long before they start canceling and censoring US Supreme Court rulings, state laws they disagree with, etc. and creating a 1984-style post-fact (2+2=5) world of lies? By having uncontested monopolies supported by the Deep State, and the NWO in general, what’s to stop them from completely undermining NATO allies and even 2nd world allies like Mexico, Brazil, India, etc.? This is World War 3.0. The digital war is fought before the physical fight, in order to take over without any shots fired, what can be taken over, and to cripple it throughout the New Cold War.

Who are the Antagonists?

Concisely we can define the enemies of Americanism, liberality, Judeo-Christianity, and western civilization in general as the following groups:

Systems	Particular Groups
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cultural Marxists ● Socialists ● Nationalists (Big Government) ● Communists ● Anarchists ● Islamists ● Fascists ● Crony/Oligarchical Capitalists ● Academia ● Socialised Education 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Antifa, BLM⁶⁴ ⁶⁵, Sunrise Movement⁶⁶ ● Democratic Socialists of America⁶⁷, Neo-nazis⁶⁸ ● Neo-cons, Big-Libs, RINOs, & alt-right ● CCP spy networks, various CCP owned NGOs ● Anarcho-communists, antifa, FBI & CIA ● The Muslim Brotherhood ● The Deep State, corporate media, FAANG ● World Bank, IMF, CCP, HSBC, Big Tech, etc. ● Harvard, Yale, any college or school system supporting segregation⁶⁹ and CRT, Teachers Unions etc.

Note who is not on the list: typical voters, moderates, centrists, independents, liberals, conservatives, anyone of particular race, sexuality, nor any western friendly system that does not seek to use terrorism to overthrow the West and liberal way of life.

⁵⁷ Over 100 businesses colluded to do so in a 48 hour period in unprecedented RICO-able conspiracy of discrimination
<https://thenewamerican.com/big-tech-censors-alex-jones-whos-next/>

⁵⁸

<https://www.newsbusters.org/blogs/free-speech/casey-ryan/2021/08/05/huge-nearly-65000-americans-submit-censorship-stories-trump>

⁵⁹ http://www.wlac.edu/online/documents/Web_2.0%20v.02.pdf

⁶⁰ Facebook (and Twitter and Instagram), Apple, Amazon, Netflix, and Google (and YouTube)

⁶¹ <https://www.foxnews.com/politics/read-trump-lawsuit-against-twitter-facebook-google-alleged-big-tech-censorship>

⁶² <https://nypost.com/2021/08/11/rand-paul-banned-from-youtube-over-anti-mask-video/>

⁶³

<https://issa.house.gov/media/press-releases/congressman-issa-declares-censorship-conservatives-singular-big-tech-crisis>

⁶⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=boS5Tw4-F9U>

⁶⁵ <https://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/2020/06/12/make-no-mistake-blm-radical-neo-marxist-political-movement/>

⁶⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DgsnyHLLdb8>

⁶⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pbNLt8UKWQA>

⁶⁸ Note how many “progressives” support segregating schools and higher education. Literally against the Civil Rights Act.

⁶⁹ <https://www.foxnews.com/us/atlanta-federal-complaint-segregation-race>

What are the Allies doing or Not doing to Prepare?

Figure 1 - the Allies

For the most part the Allies are in disarray⁷⁰. Recently “close allies” refused to buy American missile defense systems⁷¹. Below is the state of military values, and of the budgetary situation, as well as a table with a list of countries. Red is not allied strongly with the west/US, and Green is allied. The darker the color red, the worse, and the darker green the better the alliance.^{72 73}

Table 1 - Allies of the US and NATO

The Americas	Europe	Asia	Oceania	Africa
Canada	United Kingdom	Russia	Australia	Egypt
Greenland	Ireland	China	Malaysia	Sudan
Iceland	Germany	India	Indonesia	Kenya
Mexico	France	Pakistan	New Zealand	Nigeria
Brazil	Italy	South Korea	Philippines	South Africa
Costa Rica	Spain	Japan	Papua New Guinea	Zaire/Congo
Panama	Portugal	North Korea	Madagascar	Zimbabwe
Puerto Rico	Austria	Turkey	Sri Lanka	Algeria

⁷⁰ <https://www.thelibertybeacon.com/brussels-nato-and-the-globalists-are-in-total-disarray/>

⁷¹ <https://www.rand.org/blog/2020/07/japan-is-canceling-a-us-missile-defense-system.html>

⁷² <https://library.oapen.org/bitstream/id/ad3f6315-86ff-4244-bd8c-f923dd971522/632976.pdf>

⁷³ Arms sales are considered a light green alliance; no relationship will be left white

Argentina	Sweden	Iran	Taiwan	Morocco
Peru	Norway	Saudi Arabia	Guam	Tunisia
Cuba	Denmark	Iraq	Fiji	Libya
Nicaragua	Finland	Ukraine	Micronesia	Chad
Honduras	Balkans (general)	Kuwait	Marshall Is.	Ivory Coast
Haiti	Czech Republic	UAE & Yemen	Tonga	Niger
Dominican Repub.	Sardinia	Israel	Atlantia	Mali
Uruguay	Greece	Mongolia	Cape Verde	Mauritania
Paraguay	Poland	Bangladesh	Canary Islands	CAR
Venezuela	Romania	Kazakhstan	Madeira	Maghreb
Columbia	Belarus	Vietnam	Bermuda	Ethiopia
Puerto Rico	Hungary	Thailand	Azores	Somalia
Falklands	Slovakia	Singapore		Tanzania
Guatemala	Bulgaria	Cambodia		Mozambique
El Salvador	Switzerland	Burma		Botswana
Belize	Luxembourg	Laos		Namibia
Jamaica	Lithuania	Nepal		Uganda
Bahamas	Latvia	Jordan		Gabon
Guyana	Estonia	Syria		Western Sahara
Trinidad	Netherlands	Lebanon		Guinea-Bissau
Ecuador	Belgium	Armenia		Sierra Leone
		Georgia		Liberia
		Afghanistan		Ghana etc.
				Cameroon
				Zambia
				Malawi

The author is not impressed by volume of alliance, but quality. The number of red may seem small, but Africa is particularly weak and vulnerable, and after all, some of these relationships should be stronger. Much stronger.

Defense expenditure as a share of GDP

Change from 2014 to 2019. 2019 figures are estimates.

SOURCE: NATO Public Diplomacy Division. *These Allies have national laws and political agreements which call for 2% of GDP to be spent on defense annually. Estimates are expected to change accordingly.

Figure 2- Defense Expenditure as Share of GDP; credit: CNBC⁷⁴

The US pays more than its fair share of the NATO budget.⁷⁵

⁷⁴ <https://www.cnbc.com/2019/12/03/each-nato-countrys-financial-contribution-to-the-military-alliance.html>

⁷⁵ https://www.nato.int/nato_static_fl2014/assets/pdf/pdf_2019_11/20191129_pr-2019-123-en.pdf

Defense expenditure

■ NATO Europe and Canada ■ United States

SOURCE: NATO Public Diplomacy Division. Figures for 2019 are estimates.

Figure 3 - Defense expenditures, NATO vs. US (2019); credit: CNBC

DEFENSE EXPENDITURE AS A SHARE OF GDP (%) (BASED ON 2015 PRICES AND EXCHANGE RATES)

Figure 4 - NATO without the US vs. NATO guidelines; credit: CNBC⁷⁶

⁷⁶ <https://www.cnbc.com/2019/12/03/three-charts-that-show-why-trump-thinks-nato-is-a-bad-deal.html>

Catching Up to Speed

To understand where things are going, so you can make plans for your business, family, institutions, make better hiring decisions and advocate in local politics (feel free to use these resources in this document), the author wants to update you on the following sections before getting into solution sets.

Figure 5 - LOCKSTEP COVID plans, according to the World Economic Forum; credit: gracevanberkum.com⁷⁷

The New World Order Plans

The New World Order publishes its beliefs and plans. Here are some examples:

- [Project for a New American Century](#) (neocons and Big Libs) (1998)
- [Rockefeller Plans - LOCKSTEP](#) (2010)
- [World Economic Forum - The Great Reset](#) (2020)

⁷⁷ <https://www.gracevanberkum.com/post/2010-rockefeller-lock-step-document-coming-to-life-right-now-time-to-wake-up>

- [UN's Great Replacement](#) (2019)⁷⁸ ([Executive Summary](#))
- [UN's Agenda 2030](#) (2020)⁷⁹
- [EU vs. Brexit Agreement](#) (2019)⁸⁰
- [Event-201 coronavirus "simulations"](#) (2019)
- [Wuhan Military Games](#) (Oct. 2019)
- [Geoengineering Conferences](#)⁸¹ (since 2015)
- [Trilateral Commission](#) (1980)^{82 83}
- [CIA MK Ultra mind-control program](#) (1962)^{84 85}
- Please note the Bildeburgers and Bohemian Grove groups do not publish their meetings.

The Deep State

The Deep State is a much more political multicellular animal. Still, the beliefs of the Intelligence community, State Department, Justice Department, etc. are still found in various laws they support and documents they publish:

- FBI and DEA anti-patriotic publications⁸⁶, especially brochures and flyers (see Figure 6)
- CIA⁸⁷: [Kubark](#) (1963⁸⁸),⁸⁹ [MK Ultra](#)⁹⁰ (1953), [COBALT](#)⁹¹ (2003), [1794-UFOs](#)⁹² (1956) etc.^{93 94 95}
- [NSA and DNI spying upon all citizens and the world](#) (post 2001)^{96 97 98 99}
- [NASA's secret SWAT police](#)¹⁰⁰ (and other surprising agencies¹⁰¹)

⁷⁸ <https://www.un.org/en/development/desa/population/publications/ageing/replacement-migration.asp>

⁷⁹ <https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/report/2020/>

⁸⁰ <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/eu-uk-after-referendum/>

⁸¹ <https://www.cfr.org/blog/geoengineering-coming-whether-its-governed-or-not>

⁸² https://trilateral.org/download/files/brochure/Trilateral_brochure-2_7.pdf

⁸³

https://www.academia.edu/33502182/THE_TRILATERAL_COMMISSION_THE_POWER_ELITE_IN_THE_FORUM_OF_INTERNATIONAL_POLITICS_and_BUSINESS

⁸⁴

https://www.cia.gov/library/abbottabad-compound/12/129E144131F2E093FB1E441C737ACF92_SearchForTheManchurianCandidate.rtf.pdf

⁸⁵ (1977 Hearing) <https://famguardian.org/Subjects/MediaIntell/GovProp/ProjectMKUltra-95mkultra.pdf>

⁸⁶ Though some at the FBI did really important work <https://bit.ly/3m2dTPO>

⁸⁷

https://www.cia.gov/library/abbottabad-compound/13/130AEF1531746AAD6AC03EF59F91E1A1_Killing_Hope_Blum_William.pdf

⁸⁸ <https://documents.theblackvault.com/documents/terrorism/kubarkinterrogationmanual.pdf>

⁸⁹

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/305777885_KUBARK_Counterintelligence_Interrogation_Review_Observations_of_an_Interrogator_-_Lessons_Learned_and_Avenues_for_Further_Research

⁹⁰ <https://www.history.com/topics/us-government/history-of-mk-ultra>

⁹¹ <https://www.amnesty.org/download/Documents/AMR5129922015ENGLISH.PDF>

⁹² <https://documents.theblackvault.com/documents/ufos/AFD-121113-017.pdf>

⁹³ <https://www.livescience.com/40172-declassified-military-cia-secrets.html>

⁹⁴ <https://www.muckrock.com/news/archives/2017/jun/21/cias-six-most-dangerous-foia/>

⁹⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_CIA_controversies

⁹⁶

<https://www.theguardian.com/world/interactive/2013/nov/01/snowden-nsa-files-surveillance-revelations-decoded#section/1>

⁹⁷ <https://www.businessinsider.com/snowden-leaks-timeline-2016-9>

⁹⁸ <http://glenngreenwald.net/#BookDocuments>

⁹⁹ <https://www.aclu.org/nsa-documents-search?page=1>

¹⁰⁰ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ieK_Bt84KF0

¹⁰¹

<https://www.thedrive.com/the-war-zone/36343/from-nasa-to-amtrak-these-are-all-the-government-agencies-with-tactical-teams>

- [US Postal Service spying on citizens](#)¹⁰² (2021)
- [IRS persecution of conservatives](#)¹⁰³ (2008-2017) & infiltration by DSA operatives¹⁰⁴
- [Upcoming expansion of Marshalls, Secret Service, DHS](#)¹⁰⁵ and [Capitol Police](#)¹⁰⁶ (ongoing Police State; creation of a defacto “SS”¹⁰⁷ or “[stasi](#)” or “[gestapo](#)”¹⁰⁸); see: [Vaccine Passports](#) and “where are your papers comrade?”¹⁰⁹
- [Leftist prosecutors targeting of conservatives and patriots](#)¹¹⁰
- [Academia signing of redacted contracts with CCP for “Confucius Institute” spy programmes](#)¹¹¹
- [World Bank support of the CCP during embargo](#)
- [IMF attempts to replace the dollar with SDR’s](#)¹¹² [this is not a currency you can invest in]
- [Federal Reserve desire to end physical US cash](#)¹¹³ ¹¹⁴ ([ended Capital Reserve Requirements in 2020](#))
- [Democrat Party support for vaccine-passports, but not voting ID for already hackable machines](#)¹¹⁵
- [Democrat Party and others’ support for CCP](#)¹¹⁶, [FAANG](#)¹¹⁷, and [other non-American structures](#)¹¹⁸

The Muslim Brotherhood

The Muslim Brotherhood¹¹⁹ has ties to ISIS/ISIL, Taliban, Al Qaeda, Hezbollah, and many other terrorists. Their resolve to take over the west via both lying (taqiyya) and policy alliance with anti-American, anti-Israel forces, as well as via out-breeding Europeans and Americans, was published in 1991 by the New York Times. A selection will be reproduced here. Please note this includes the group known as CAIR which Congresswoman and brother-marrier Ilhan Omar¹²⁰ said was created after 9/11 due to islamophobia.¹²¹ In fact the group was in existence *by plan* since 1994, the year of the WTC bombing. It was clear gaslighting by a

¹⁰² <https://www.eff.org/press/releases/eff-sues-us-postal-service-records-about-covert-social-media-spying-program>

¹⁰³ <https://www.npr.org/2017/10/27/560308997/irs-apologizes-for-aggressive-scrutiny-of-conservative-groups>

¹⁰⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BUuUWFANPS8>

¹⁰⁵ As the author wrote this, the Department of Homeland Security randomly released this alert, naming specifically Trump supporters, or those who question the election and the obvious fraud involved, as potential terrorist threats, though “no credible threats” were current. They are maneuvering against patriotic people, renewing the FBI’s past activity:

https://www.dhs.gov/sites/default/files/ntas/alerts/21_0813_ntas_bulletin_all-sectors.pdf

¹⁰⁶ <https://www.yahoo.com/now/capitol-police-expansion-california-florida-014000738.html>

¹⁰⁷ <https://encyclopedia.ushmm.org/content/en/article/ss-police-state>

¹⁰⁸ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Gestapo>

¹⁰⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uqp2jhW6BY8>

¹¹⁰ <https://www.fbi.gov/wanted/capitol-violence>; the irony is the FBI and Capitol Police instigated the situation to entrap citizens

¹¹¹ Example: University of Kentucky <https://bit.ly/3BhuWT5>

¹¹² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rUAACHLbFo4>

¹¹³ <https://www.federalreserve.gov/newsevents/pressreleases/bcreg20210325a.htm>

¹¹⁴ <https://www.federalreserve.gov/newsevents/speech/waller20210805a.htm>

¹¹⁵

<https://www.politico.com/magazine/story/2016/08/2016-elections-russia-hack-how-to-hack-an-election-in-seven-minutes-214144/>

¹¹⁶ <https://sanfrancisco.cbslocal.com/2018/08/01/details-chinese-spy-dianne-feinstein-san-francisco/>

¹¹⁷ <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/newsletters/2021-03-19/why-big-tech-should-worry-next-china>

¹¹⁸ <https://www.hrw.org/report/2017/09/05/costs-international-advocacy/chinas-interference-united-nations-human-rights>

¹¹⁹ <https://www.documentcloud.org/documents/228562-elbarasse-search-3.html>

¹²⁰

<https://www.dailymail.co.uk/news/article-8013283/Ilhan-Omar-DID-marry-brother-reveals-Somali-community-leader.html>

¹²¹ <https://www.washingtonpost.com/politics/2019/04/11/some-people-did-something-rep-omars-remarks-context/>

known member of the Muslim Brotherhood who is also in Congress. She has committed actual fraud, and gotten away with it.¹²²

“The leadership of the U.S. Muslim Brotherhood (MB, or Ikhwan) has said that its goal was and is jihad aimed at destroying the U.S. from within. The Brotherhood leadership has also said that the means of achieving this goal is to establish Islamic organizations in the U.S. under the control of the Muslim Brotherhood. Since the early 1960s, the Brotherhood has constructed an elaborate covert organizational infrastructure on which was built a set of public or “front” organizations. The current U.S. Brotherhood leadership has attempted to deny this history, both claiming that it is not accurate and at the same time that saying that it represents an older form of thought inside the Brotherhood. An examination of public and private Brotherhood documents, however, indicates that this history is both accurate and that the Brotherhood has taken no action to demonstrate change in its mode of thought and/or activity”

*... A 1991 document written by U.S. MB leader Mohammed Akram (a.k.a. Mohammed Adlouni) explains the goal of the Brotherhood in America, **which he identifies as “settlement:**” The general strategic goal of the Brotherhood in America which was approved by the Shura [Leadership] Council and the Organizational Conference for 1987 is “enablement of Islam in North America, meaning: establishing an effective and stable Islamic Movement led by the Muslim Brotherhood which adopts Muslims’ causes domestically and globally, and which works to expand the observant Muslim base; aims at unifying and directing Muslims’ efforts; presents Islam as a civilization alternative; and supports the **global Islamic state**, wherever it is.”*

*... The priority that is approved by the Shura Council for the work of the Brotherhood in its current and former session is “Settlement.”¹ [2] Center on Islam, Democracy, and the Future of the Muslim World The document goes on to explain that **“settlement” is a form of jihad aimed at destroying Western civilization from within** and allowing for the victory of Islam over other religions: The process of settlement is a “Civilization-Jihadist process” with all that the word means. The Ikhwan must understand that their work in America is a kind of grand Jihad in eliminating and destroying the Western civilization from within and “sabotaging” its miserable house by their hands and the hands of the believers so that it is eliminated and God’s religion is **made victorious over all other religions**. Without this level of understanding, we are not up to this challenge and have not prepared ourselves for Jihad yet. It is a Muslim’s destiny to perform Jihad and work wherever he is and wherever he lands until the final hour comes, and there is no escape from that destiny except for those who chose to slack. But, would the slackers and the Mujahidin be equal.²*

*... In another part of the document titled “The Process of Settlement,” the author explains that for the Brotherhood’s goals to be accomplished, it is necessary to have a **strong organizational base:** In order for Islam and its Movement to become “a **part of the homeland**” in which it lives, “stable” in its land, “rooted” in the spirits and minds of its people, “enabled” in the life of its society, [with] firmly established “organizations” on which the Islamic structure is built and with which the testimony of civilization is achieved, the Movement must plan and struggle to obtain “the keys” and the tools of this process in carrying out this grand mission as a “Civilization-Jihadist” responsibility which lies on the shoulders of Muslims and—on top of them—the Muslim Brotherhood in this country....”¹²³ (emphasis added)*

As the document is self-explanatory, and the commentary document fills in the gaps, the author need say no more. It is **a foreign invasion scheme, plain and simple.**

¹²²

<https://www.twincities.com/2020/09/28/project-veritas-video-alleges-widespread-voter-fraud-in-mn-with-u-s-rep-ilhan-omar-at-head/>

¹²³ https://www.globalmbresearch.com/wp-content/uploads/2015/03/20090411_merley.usbrotherhood.pdf

Side Players

Unfortunately, well intentioned liberals often get roped into “progressivism”¹²⁴ not knowing the sordid history of progressivism¹²⁵ in the early 20th century Communist revolutions.¹²⁶ Quite commonly they get involved in well-sounding movements, with mottos like “black lives matter”¹²⁷ which are actually full Communist corporations,^{128 129 130 131} in order to lead well meaning and open-minded liberals into rioting and fomenting extreme terrorism.^{132 133 134} Often it doesn’t go beyond petty crime¹³⁵, but often does involve violence¹³⁶, felonious activity¹³⁷, arson¹³⁸, and politically¹³⁹ or racially motivated¹⁴⁰ terroristic¹⁴¹ crime¹⁴² which was already criminal even before 9/11 and attendant PATRIOT bills.¹⁴³ Now, those bills are being used to create ambiguity about the concept of terrorism¹⁴⁴ which targets people on the right^{145 146 147} and sets free leftist anarchists and communists who involve themselves in actual textbook terrorism.^{148 149 150 151}

¹²⁴ <https://www.thepublicdiscourse.com/2017/01/18550/>

¹²⁵ <https://newrepublic.com/article/128144/dark-history-liberal-reform>

¹²⁶ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/2698847/>

¹²⁷ While black lives *do* matter, and *should* matter, obviously All Lives Matter (or none do). Nevertheless, saying “Yes, black lives do matter” is not concise, although it is certainly less lazy. Sadly, this distinction has caused much controversy and friction, even within the black community let alone without it. Black Christians are understandably upset with the monolith created by the corporate motto and communist term.

<https://www.tennessean.com/story/opinion/2020/08/20/southern-baptist-leader-richard-land-response-black-lives-matter-movement/5616017002/>

¹²⁸ https://www.supremecourt.gov/DocketPDF/19/19-1108/141260/20200409134118279_19-1108BriefOfRespondent.pdf

¹²⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ekt6n0VMI3s>

¹³⁰ <http://stateofthenation.co/?p=27580>

¹³¹ <https://www.insider.com/what-is-thousand-currents-black-lives-matter-charity-2020-6>

¹³²

<https://apnews.com/article/george-floyd-race-and-ethnicity-new-york-mn-state-wire-racial-injustice-1d5d09286d910bc84c48ffe2d3a11197>

¹³³

<https://www.heritage.org/progressivism/commentary/blm-co-founder-and-pro-communist-china-group-are-partnering-heres-why>

¹³⁴ <https://www.heritage.org/progressivism/commentary/fact-checking-new-york-times-fact-checker-blms-china-links>

¹³⁵

<https://townhall.com/tipsheet/juliorosas/2021/05/05/blm-protester-pulls-gun-on-louisville-dinners-one-dinner-pulls-out-their-own-gun-n2588985>

¹³⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Shooting_of_David_Dorn

¹³⁷ <https://theinformedyouth.weebly.com/politics/target-that-was-burned-by-blm-last-year-now-has-mural-celebrating-arson>

¹³⁸ <https://www.breitbart.com/2020-election/2020/09/23/report-biden-supporters-burn-home-minnesota/>

¹³⁹ <https://www.redvoicemedia.com/2021/08/blm-protestors-target-tucker-at-fox-news-hq-burn-american-flag/>

¹⁴⁰ <https://www.cnsnews.com/commentary/hans-bader/blm-protesters-deface-statue-war-hero-who-helped-blacks>

¹⁴¹ <https://www.newsweek.com/white-jesus-statues-should-torn-down-black-lives-matters-leader-says-1512674>

¹⁴²

<https://www.dailymail.co.uk/news/article-8654761/Truck-driver-beaten-BLM-protesters-Portland-said-took-10-minutes-police-up.html>

¹⁴³ <https://nypost.com/2020/08/17/blm-mob-beat-white-man-unconscious-after-making-him-crash-truck/>

¹⁴⁴ <https://fleetingfreedom.com/index.php/2021/01/09/democrats-rush-to-redefine-political-dissent-as-terrorism/>

¹⁴⁵ <https://www.ohchr.org/Documents/Publications/Factsheet32EN.pdf>

¹⁴⁶ <https://www.fema.gov/pdf/areyouready/terrorism.pdf>

¹⁴⁷ <https://www.fbi.gov/history/brief-history/a-world-of-trouble>

¹⁴⁸

<https://www.msn.com/en-us/news/us/black-lives-matter-has-terrorist-and-communist-inspirations-but-liberal-media-doesn-e2-80-99t-care/ar-BB18PJUI>

¹⁴⁹ <https://nypost.com/2021/05/21/black-lives-matters-obscene-support-for-hamas-terrorism/>

¹⁵⁰ <https://www.complex.com/life/not-fucking-around-coalition-grandmaster-jay-explainer>

¹⁵¹

<https://100percentfedup.com/breaking-black-lives-matter-agitator-punches-black-trump-supporter-in-the-face-is-immediately-arrested-video/>

Right Wing Extremists

- "defenders" of US Constitution against federal government and the UN (Super Patriots)
- Groups of individuals engaged in para-military training

Hate Groups

- Skinheads, Nazis, Neo-Nazis (usually recognized by tattoos)
- Black Separatists
- KKK
- Christian Identity
- White Nationalists

Common Law Movement Proponents

- Fictitious license plates
- No license plates
- Fictitious drivers license
- No drivers license
- Refuse to identify themselves
- Request authority for stop
- Make numerous references to US Constitution
- Claim driving is a right, not a privilege
- Attempt to "police the police"

Left-Wing Terrorists

- Political motivation is usually Marxist/Leninist philosophy

Macheteros

Single Issue Terrorists

- Targeting of law enforcement and emergency personnel
- Animal Rights
- Eco-terrorism
- Violent anti-abortion extremism
- Urban riot agitators
- Cyber penetration
- Non-Aligned Terrorists
- Doomsday/Cult-Type Group
- Insurgents/Rebels
- Lone Individuals

Weapons of Mass Destruction

- Nuclear
- Chemical
- Biological

Figure 6 - How the FBI Deep State division likes to define terrorism; credit: FBI

Modern Industrialized Slavery

There is a well documented strain of pedo-philia¹⁵² and Satanism^{153 154} underway. Equally as appalling, sex slavery, human trafficking, including at the US border and ignored by "progressives" like Rep. Cortez, Tlaib etc., and actual human slavery going from Africa into Europe¹⁵⁵ has been well documented¹⁵⁶. But of these, the

¹⁵²

https://drive.google.com/file/d/0ByRZ_FN_vit_UUtkV0VqMmBVE0/view?usp=sharing&resourcekey=0-G55gMwd-nvgiDikWsE9gcQ

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1klorlImAmaQsYLI5AOKKpWxp6HJ9giak/view?usp=sharing>

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1HPFdAW02D8cYIGfInRbeLQ3UIBVFDsSE/view?usp=sharing>

https://drive.google.com/file/d/0ByRZ_FN_vit_eUICd2NCREhCSWM/view?usp=sharing&resourcekey=0-ReMmtjgVbcEhJt_gU9AWAUQ

¹⁵³

https://drive.google.com/file/d/0ByRZ_FN_vit_THN3MzY5MXRIZjg/view?usp=sharing&resourcekey=0-s42w1aXHd0Xug9ZUOTlsxg

¹⁵⁴ <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1DJ8tN8UPUUAJQxKqbA7XaDoyTG7M4zLw/view?usp=sharing>

¹⁵⁵ <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-39567632>

¹⁵⁶ <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/2158244019828849>

child porn industry¹⁵⁷ (and from out of movie makers¹⁵⁸), Haitian child sex slave traffic^{159 160 161 162} to support this massive industry,^{163 164} is as reprehensible and serious¹⁶⁵ as the human organ trafficking industry¹⁶⁶, which is strongly propped up by the Communists of the CCP^{167 168 169}, and other southeast Asia military tyrannical regimes.¹⁷⁰

Neocolonialism

Furthermore, beyond the anti-Muslim (Uighar) and anti-Falun Gong organ harvesting of the CCP¹⁷¹, they are also involved in colonizing far flung minorities and foreigners of weaker nations, such as in Africa¹⁷², the stans¹⁷³, Sri Lanka¹⁷⁴, Oceania¹⁷⁵, and Central America¹⁷⁶. This is part of a greater imperialism strain on the rise, which is a strong departure from the League of Nations¹⁷⁷ and Geneva Accords¹⁷⁸, as a world order and belief in fundamental human rights.¹⁷⁹

Future Empires

The most surprising and frightening development is the strengthening of ties between Putin (former KGB) and China¹⁸⁰, as well as a host of Axis players with long histories of fascism etc: Iran, Italy, N. Korea, Vietnam, Venezuela, multiple African regimes^{181 182}, etc. If the CCP bought out the Russian empire and remnants of the Czarism that remain in the former USSR, what kind of Big Tech type fascist empire could be created?

The author shudders to think of it.

¹⁵⁷ <https://www.fbi.gov/video-repository/seattle-trafficking-survivor062618.mp4/view>

¹⁵⁸ <https://www.foxnews.com/opinion/netflix-cuties-child-pornography-hollywood-exploitation-sen-tom-cotton>

¹⁵⁹ <https://www.thelastamericanvagabond.com/clinton-silsby-trafficking-scandal-media-attempted-ignorecover/>

¹⁶⁰

<https://www.investmentwatchblog.com/wikileaks-convicted-child-abductor-was-caught-stealing-children-in-haiti-with-the-clintons/>

¹⁶¹

<https://fightingmonarch.files.wordpress.com/2021/07/heres-an-archived-version-of-the-clinton-silsby-trafficking-scandal-and-the-media-cover-up-the-true-origin-of-pizzagate.pdf>

¹⁶² <https://archive.thinkprogress.org/100-000-children-are-forced-into-prostitution-each-year-97472b01a9d/>

¹⁶³ <https://www.humanrightsfirst.org/resource/human-trafficking-numbers>

¹⁶⁴

https://www.rutherford.org/publications_resources/john_whiteheads_commentary/americas_dirty_little_secret_sex_trafficking_is_big_business

¹⁶⁵ <https://www.tvcnews.tv/human-trafficking-is-a-150-billion-a-year-global-industry-unodc/>

¹⁶⁶ https://www.unodc.org/documents/human-trafficking/UNVTF_fs_HT_EN.pdf

¹⁶⁷ <https://bigthink.com/politics-current-affairs/china-organ-harvesting>

¹⁶⁸ <https://www.chinasucks.net/organ-trade-in-china/>

¹⁶⁹ <https://faluninfo.net/wall-street-journal-the-nightmare-of-human-organ-harvesting-in-china/>

¹⁷⁰ <https://www.imf.org/external/pubs/ft/fandd/2018/09/human-trafficking-in-southeast-asia-caballero.htm>

¹⁷¹ <https://www.businessinsider.com/china-harvesting-organs-of-uighur-muslims-china-tribunal-tells-un-2019-9?op=1>

¹⁷² <https://www.panafricanalliance.com/china-africa-colonialism/>

¹⁷³ <https://tfipost.com/2019/11/chinas-belt-and-road-is-destroying-central-asia-and-people-are-out-to-protest/>

¹⁷⁴ <https://international.thenewslens.com/article/59105>

¹⁷⁵ <https://www.thetrumpet.com/24015-china-is-not-finished-colonizing-the-spratlys>

¹⁷⁶ <https://www.nytimes.com/2020/11/08/world/americas/china-caribbean.html>

¹⁷⁷ <https://www.history.com/topics/world-war-i/league-of-nations>

¹⁷⁸ <https://www.thoughtco.com/the-geneva-accords-1954-3310118>

¹⁷⁹ <https://www.timesofisrael.com/critics-slam-un-human-rights-councils-election-of-unqualified-new-members/>

¹⁸⁰ <https://www.politico.com/story/2019/06/05/china-russia-xi-jinping-vladimir-putin-1353546>

¹⁸¹ <https://rightscorridor.com/why-african-governments-agree-with-chinas-view-on-human-rights/>

¹⁸² <http://www.cadtm.org/China-s-role-in-amplifying-Southern-Africa-s-extreme-uneven-development>

Solution Sets

The following short list is what the author thinks, based on art of war studies and other analyses, will increase vaccination against all the bad ideas, and save the West for the future.

Table 2 - Solution sets; Red is Attack, Green is Support, Blue is Neutralize

Individual Solutions	Family Solutions	Social Solutions	Political Solutions
<p>Read:</p> <input type="checkbox"/> "Hundred Year Marathon"	<p>Judeo-Christians: breed</p>	<p>Promote real cosmologies and history</p>	<p>Libertarians should join the Democrat Party</p>
<input type="checkbox"/> "Stealth War"	<p>Educate kids about drugs properly¹⁸⁵</p>	<p>Strengthen ties with neighbors</p>	<p>Republicans should unify with independents</p>
<input type="checkbox"/> "Deceiving the Sky"	<p>Homeschool</p>	<p>Setup Farmer's Markets</p>	<p>Independents remove RINOs and neocons</p>
<input type="checkbox"/> "Secret Empires"	<p>Co-ops</p>	<p>Promote sustainable communities</p>	<p>Support term limits</p>
<input type="checkbox"/> "New Case for Gold"	<p>Setup prep circles</p>	<p>Promote STEM</p>	<p>Attack corruption on any level by anyone</p>
<input type="checkbox"/> "Atlas Shrugged"	<p>Use Farm CSAs</p>	<p>Discourage "snitching" especially regarding COVID/vaccines</p>	<p>Collect and release digital evidence</p>
<input type="checkbox"/> "Grunch of Giants"	<p>Start spiritual study groups</p>	<p>Attack pedophilia</p>	<p>Form alliances</p>
<input type="checkbox"/> "How to Destroy America in Three Easy Steps"	<p>Promote modernized education</p>	<p>Attack industrial abortion</p>	<p>Promote militias</p>
<input type="checkbox"/> "Unrestricted Warfare"	<p>Promote classical education of Greek, Roman, etc. history</p>	<p>Attack anti-patriotism</p>	<p>Attack the Police State</p>
<input type="checkbox"/> "Thick Face, Black Heart"	<p>Teach kids about Republic histories</p>	<p>Attack nationalism</p>	<p>Attack the Deep State</p>
<p>Train in firearms use</p>	<p>Strengthen ties with family & extended family</p>	<p>Attack institutions that are designed to attack churches and traditions and the right to bear arms</p>	<p>Attack the NWO</p>
<p>Train in survival skills</p>	<p>Lead church and school PTSA functions</p>	<p>Support pro-life and wholesome programs</p>	<p>Support Property Rights</p>
<p>Train in Self-defense¹⁸³</p>			<p>Support the Bill of Rights</p>
<p>Play strategy games</p>			<p>Support real Liberalism</p>
<p>Use Signal, Telegram, Discord, etc.</p>			
<p>Promote digital security</p>			
<p>Use cryptocurrencies¹⁸⁴</p>			

Value Systems Wars (Culture Wars)

Studies show that the majority of minorities in America are *also* Christian leaning¹⁸⁶, not foreign religious leaning.¹⁸⁷ Yet there is a strange, racially driven (white-hating) narrative that Christian = White and so any pro-American + pro-Christian must be a white supremacist.^{188 189 190 191} In fact, groups like the Proud Boys

¹⁸³ <https://bit.ly/2Uh6ReL>

¹⁸⁴

https://www.academia.edu/47732738/Simple_Guide_for_Friends_Family_and_Common_Folk_of_how_to_get_into_Crypto

¹⁸⁵ Preaching abstinence doesn't work; you need to be honest with kids about the different types of drugs and which ones God created (like Marijuana and Mushrooms) and which are man-made abominations (meth, bath salts, heroine, etc.)

¹⁸⁶

<https://www.pewresearch.org/fact-tank/2018/04/23/black-americans-are-more-likely-than-overall-public-to-be-christian-practicing/>

¹⁸⁷ <https://www.pewresearch.org/topic/religion/>

¹⁸⁸ All 3 next footnotes make the author sick <https://www.patheos.com/blogs/teaaddictedwitch/2019/07/toxic-christianity/>

¹⁸⁹ <https://www.sfexaminer.com/news-columnists/why-would-any-jew-be-a-republican/>

¹⁹⁰ <https://washingtonmonthly.com/magazine/july-august-2018/how-the-right-wing-convinces-itself-that-liberals-are-evil/>

¹⁹¹ While it may be true that many white, male, Republicans do this... the unabashed shame of equating the entire group with heinous terms like racism, while being themselves racist, is probably the greatest example of what is wrong with the left today. They engage in **blatant discrimination** and then ask "why is the kettle black?" They create the divide, despite all previous bi-partisan support (indeed Civil Rights *came from the Republican Party*) and then attack the right for having

may be led by hispanics¹⁹² ¹⁹³, and full of African Americans¹⁹⁴, and yet get labeled by leftist NGOs (like Southern Poverty Law Center¹⁹⁵) as “white supremacist” with little to no proof.¹⁹⁶

What they are really saying is that such groups, being patriotic and pro-American Culture, pro-American History and pro-American Philosophy... are too Christian, and too anti-Socialist, etc. The most convenient way to attack the American DNA is to make it racial, sexual, or other identity (toxic) politics that utilize the key portion of critical theories¹⁹⁷ in order to divide and conquer otherwise united groups of people. By values and culture, hispanics are pro Christian, pro nuclear family, and very Conservative.¹⁹⁸ But to control this population the Democrat Party (DPAC) uses strong reverse racism imagery to make the Republicans (the party of the original Civil Rights Bill¹⁹⁹ and anti-Jim Crow²⁰⁰) seem racist and “too white”. This idea itself is notoriously racist, so over 30 years, as Yuri Bezmenov (former KGB) predicted²⁰¹: the left simply redefines racism, sexism, etc. in order to isolate whites, especially white males (the most productive group of engineers and scientists for 200 years), and also heterosexual males of any color (population control). By doing so, the groups become increasingly narrow, specialized, contradictory (LGB vs. TQ²⁰²), into easily controlled political slaves to the one party system. Furthermore the left’s “useful idiots”²⁰³ get mobilized and motivated through hatred and anger, which is far more revolution-inducing than “peaceful protests.”²⁰⁴

Preparing Your Family & Friends (Inoculation)

There’s an unfortunate feeling that the only way to get along with friends and family who are either infected by all these bad ideas or vehemently against them (both equally loud), is to avoid politics and religion discussions on social media, or avoid all of social media. This is, unfortunately, not a good response. Because politics works by loudness, it is important for patriots, centrists, independents, moderates, paleo-conservatives, paleo-liberals, and modern Democrats and Republicans (as opposed to postmodern), to speak up and say “we are the 85% and no you do not get to tell me how to live my life.”

To do so, please share this paper, resources, and the future book, and make people aware that “the road to Hell is paved with good intentions.” Find the areas where you have agreement, and then promote open

division. The left/right divide was always there. But the research shows, it was the Left that left the center behind.

<https://assets.pewresearch.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/5/2017/10/05162647/10-05-2017-Political-landscape-release.pdf>

¹⁹² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Enrique_Tarrio

¹⁹³

<https://www.dailymail.co.uk/news/article-8794301/Leader-Proud-Boys-state-director-Latinos-Trump-close-ties-GOP.html>

¹⁹⁴

<https://twitichy.com/gregp-3534/2020/10/01/i-didnt-see-this-coming-black-proud-boys-members-respond-to-joe-biden-calling-them-white-supremacists/>

¹⁹⁵ The tech Left have not figured out that Patriotism is not a White thing; that’s how controlled the Left is by Socialism.

<https://www.thedailybeast.com/why-young-men-of-color-are-joining-white-supremacist-groups>

¹⁹⁶

<https://atlantablackstar.com/2018/10/24/who-are-the-proud-boys-and-why-are-nonwhite-men-joining-white-supremacist-groups>

¹⁹⁷ Criticism puts people on the defensive, usually unnecessarily, and this weakens their positional advantage at the outset.

¹⁹⁸ <https://nypost.com/2021/01/23/why-the-us-hispanic-conservative-movement-is-surg-ing-even-without-trump/>

Searching about this topic is amusing: so many leftist publications are fuming about the GOP horning in on their imported base of future voters. The way the DPAC tries to literally own minorities, LBGTQ, and women is really disgusting.

¹⁹⁹ <https://www.glennbeck.com/2015/04/28/the-real-history-of-the-civil-rights-movement/>

²⁰⁰ <https://thekeep.eiu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?referer=&httpsredir=1&article=3677&context=theses>

²⁰¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yErKTVdETpw>

²⁰² L, G, and B ... and T all believe in only two genders (science based); non-binary Trans and Q all believe in intersectional feminism, which denies the feminine and promotes any number of genders. Yuri explains why:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TEefbbApuaE>

²⁰³ Yuri also explain they are killed after Normalization is complete <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Z1EA2ohrt5Q>

²⁰⁴ Or as the Left puts it “mostly peaceful protests” See: CHAZ

<https://www.lifezette.com/2020/06/a-murder-in-seattles-mostly-peaceful-chaz-chop-insurrection-sector/>

dialogue much in the vein that Ben Shapiro (Jewish Conservative) was able to have with liberal Russel Brand²⁰⁵. Even where debates can get toxic, support the open forums and attack - vehemently and forcefully - those who only use identity politics, critical theories, and ad hominem, particularly from the position of assuming moral authority by throwing out words that are blatantly misused or lied about, such as: racist, sexist, misogynist, homophobe, islamophobe, etc.

Also, where possible, **support the right to bear arms**. In places where that right is suspended, totalitarianism follows (Australia^{206 207}, China, Ireland), and the ally becomes weak²⁰⁸, and one step closer to genocide.^{209 210 211 212}

Action Steps Checklist

The follow is a checklist of things you can do, starting today, to spread pro-American, pro-Western, pro-Democracy, pro-Republic, pro-Capitalism (healthy) strains of thought, action, and social activities:

- Learn Civics
 - Read the book "How to Destroy America in Three Easy Steps"²¹³ and learn American History, Culture, and Philosophy - **get psyched/amped about Western Democracies!**
 - Read the [Federalist Papers](#) and the [founding documents of the US](#) and [Western democracies](#)
 - Read the [Magna Carta](#)
 - Participate in local politics and civics
 - Learn to debate in a classical pre-Internet sense; learn dialectics²¹⁴
 - Call your state, federal, provincial, and national representatives
 - Learn Due Process²¹⁵ and [support all your rights](#), *vocally and physically*
- Practice militia²¹⁶ and military arts
 - Form airsoft/paintball teams²¹⁷
 - Study martial arts, boxing, wrestling, etc.
 - Spend time with policemen²¹⁸ in society and convert them away from the Police State
 - Educate Juries²¹⁹ & Sheriff departments about their veto rights²²⁰
 - Know your rights: warrants, search & seizure, and the power of silence²²¹.
 - [Join the National Guard](#)
 - Support your right to bear arms

²⁰⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7Kn-yzr5We4>

²⁰⁶

<https://www.westernjournal.com/looks-like-people-facing-total-medical-tyranny-military-rolls-major-city-enforce-covid-lockdowns/>

²⁰⁷ <https://themadruther.com/2021/08/10/military-enforcement-of-covid-tyranny-comes-to-australia/>

²⁰⁸ <https://www.businessinsider.com/2nd-amendment-countries-constitutional-right-bear-arms-2017-10?op=1>

²⁰⁹ https://theacru.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/03/ACRU_GunControl_v3b.pdf

²¹⁰ <https://www.theculturewatch.com/gun-control-disarmament-and-the-threat-of-genocide>

²¹¹ <http://lookintoit.org/Gun-Control-Leads-To-Genocide.html>

²¹² <https://thenewamerican.com/the-racist-origin-of-america-s-gun-control-laws/>

²¹³ Ben Shapiro, 2020

²¹⁴ <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/hegel-dialectics/>

²¹⁵ <https://www.law.cornell.edu/constitution-conan/amendment-14/section-1/due-process-of-law>

²¹⁶ As per suggestion of Gen. Westmoreland (1994)

<https://archive.org/details/how-to-start-and-train-a-militia-unit-george-westmoreland-1994>

²¹⁷ <https://bit.ly/3AIVpbs>

²¹⁸ Talk to them as people; go on ride-alongs

²¹⁹ <https://www.copblock.org/36017/an-essay-on-the-trial-by-jury/>

²²⁰ <https://theappeal.org/the-power-of-sheriffs-an-explainer/>

²²¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=d-7o9xYp7eE>

- NRA, GOA, etc.
- Go to local stores and shooting ranges
- Encourage Congress to support ALL of the Bill of Rights²²²
- Study [the Arts of War](#)²²³
 - Study strategy²²⁴ and games²²⁵
 - Learn about Positional Advantage²²⁶
- Prepare
 - [Cybersecurity checklist](#)
 - [Home and security checklist](#)
 - Resiliency in general
 - Permaculture etc.
 - Food and water prep & stock
 - Ammo stock
 - Energy generation techniques
- Participate in Capitalism
 - Become an entrepreneur
 - Become a serial entrepreneur
 - Learn finance, capital, and economics
 - Staunchly oppose lies** such as “democratic socialism” or pro-inflation arguments
 - Most especially call out those using racism incorrectly or under historical revisionism
 - Most especially those using said definition to commit further acts of bigotry
 - Verbally call out hypocrisy about capitalism (where they decry it while using laptops, internet, and drinking Starbucks)
 - Support as little as possible the power of Big Tech, but retain utility as needed.²²⁷

Author Further Recommends

Whenever red-pilling family, or black-pilling anyone about conspiracies, it is important to remember to not be/seem crazy or act in a lunatic manner. First, you may risk misrepresenting the patriotic community and therefore individual liberty etc. Second, it can become draining, toxic, or distractive. Stick always to “means, motive and opportunity” to understand groups and conspiracies, and never pick on their ethnicities even when attacking fairly defined groups. For example, do not attack Arabs or Palestinians, when you mean Islamists and terrorists. Do not attack Asians or use racial epithets (like chinks or towelheads, etc.) when you mean certain political structures, such as the Chinese Communist Party, or ISIS, or the Muslim Brotherhood. These are the toxic tactics of anti-American, anti-Westerners, and also the fuel and fodder of white supremacists, black supremacists, and other groups which divide people as equally well by conditions that individuals cannot control (ie, their race, color, sex, etc.) Use your freedom of expression responsibly.

Figure 7 - Roll Safe.

²²² Because the ACLU won't! <https://www.aclu.org/other/second-amendment> This is flat out WRONG as per DC v Heller

²²³ <https://bit.ly/3xllkxJ> Enjoy!

²²⁴ https://www.academia.edu/40287817/Understanding_Chess_I_The_Art_of_Chess

²²⁵ https://www.academia.edu/42613756/Chinese_Checkers_as_an_Underrated_Strategy_Game

²²⁶ https://www.academia.edu/50357891/MIMS_and_Shi

²²⁷ For example, this was written on Google Docs

In the same vein, when attacking the language butchers from the LGBTQ lobby, or identifying grooming and pedophilia, do not mix these with specific religious beliefs, such as Christian anti-homosexual rhetoric. If you are against abortion, stick to socialism and genocide, and murder as the discussion instead of attacking women. Similarly, if you are against homosexuality on a moral level, be careful to respectfully separate your feelings about a lifestyle from the person's personal sexual identity. If they are trans, focus upon their obvious belief in two genders, and a desire to live their own life as a basis for healthy liberal support, rather than upon flamboyance or other factors of personal judgment in order to participate in the same divide and conquer that the progressives use to create toxic cancel culture. In other words: be careful with your words. If you write, define and cite everything you can.

In general, learn the totality of Positional Advantage²²⁸, and be courageous. If you are a strong Christian, be **unapologetic** about it, and use appropriate non-hypocritical language *and* humor. Make friends with even atheists of the west. Christians should not be mean-spirited.

However, if you are not loaded down with some specific humanistic paradigm, also seek first to be a dialoguer over using ad hominem in debate tactics. The more you understand Optics, the better it will be. But, also learn to **play dirty, mean, hit below the belt, and use the Rule of Law** both as a support for argument, and as a weapon against terrorists, anarchists, real racists, etc.

If you have your military and martial art skills up, and keep your private belief in a right to bear arms to defend your home, family, God, and country, then you have little to fear, and no reason to participate in: mass shootings, racial hate-parades, etc. Do not give your enemies the right to hang your friends and family, by feeding the narratives of the enemies of the West!²²⁹

Figure 8 - Michael Jordan telling "Progressives" and the infected with zombie/anti-west virus to "stop it, get some help."

Conclusion

In conclusion, the author feels that though the right side is losing the current Cold War, it has the ability to use freedom, intelligence, and the larger population to adapt quickly, and to survive. However, to do so, the 85% will have to quickly learn to be aggressive-assertive, stop being passive (no matter how well intentioned, or how busy a well employed and self-regulating citizen may be), and **be present and aware**. They will need to first become educated about the New Cold War, and aware of its massive implications, and willing to share this information.

If this document is followed, then it will lead to victory in 20, 30, or 50 years. But patience will be key, as well as prompt action.

²²⁸ <https://2001-2009.state.gov/documents/organization/96437.pdf>

²²⁹ For example: do not join neo-nazis, white supremacists, become "Sovereign Citizens", join cults, etc. Do not ramble on extensively about the "Jewish problem." You're not helping regular liberals to think like patriots by conflating your bigotry with patriotism!

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